

README

All files are gathered in `dataset_and_scripts.zip`.

All scripts are written for python 3.7.7. Required python packages are:

- *numpy* (1.21.6), *pandas* (1.3.5), *matplotlib* (3.5.1), *scipy* (1.7.3), *json5* (0.9.5), *openpyxl* (3.0.7), *uncertainties* (3.1.6), *cmcrameri* (1.5), *mpl_point_clicker* (0.3.1), *opencv-python* (4.2.0.34), *pywin32* (227)
- *core_tools* version 1.4.29 (https://github.com/stephanphilips/core_tools)
- *pulse_lib* version 1.5.5 (https://github.com/stephanphilips/pulse_lib)

The plots included in the figures can be created by opening *figure_plots_script.py* (e.g. in Spyder) and executing it cell by cell. To reproduce the plots shown in the supplementary figures please execute *figure_plots_supplementary_script.py* cell by cell.

Raw data is located in the folder *raw_data*, descriptions and additional parameters belonging to the raw data can be found in *data_overview_sheets*. The folder *point_archive* stores json files containing clicked charge triple degeneracy points, clicked points to determine relative lever arms from charge stability diagrams, and clicked points to determine absolute lever arms from coulomb diamonds. Also, the COMSOL simulation underlying the schematic figure S4 (in supplementary section S5) is provided.